

PERSONALITY TRAITS OF PROSPECTIVE TEACHERS

Dr. R. Boopathi

Assistant Professor, Department of Educational Technology, Tamil Nadu Teachers
Education University, Chennai, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: Dr. R. Boopathi, "Personality Traits of Prospective Teachers",
International Journal of Computational Research and Development, Volume 3, Issue 2, Page
Number 37-40, 2018.

Abstract:

An admirable teaching personality is one in which the teacher's personality contributes to the creation and maintenance of a classroom or learning environment in which pupils are happy and motivated to study. The personality traits enhance teaching because even when there is no verbal contact between the instructor and the student, communication does occur. The purpose of this research is to determine the level of whole personality traits in total and other traits like extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism and openness of prospective teachers with respect to gender. A total of three hundred and three prospective teachers from ten different B.Ed colleges in Salem and Namakkal Districts of Tamilnadu are taking part in the study. The research tool Big Five Personality Inventory designed and standardized by John, O. P., and Srivastava, S. (1999) was utilized to collect the data. The findings indicated that the majority of prospective teachers have average personality traits in total and other traits. Gender influences the personality traits in total, extraversion, openness, and neuroticism. The female prospective teachers have low neuroticism scores which show that they are more stable and emotionally resilient when compared to their male counterparts. Individuals with high levels of this attribute are more likely to have mood swings, anxiety, impatience, and sorrow. The highest score of neuroticism of male counterparts which resembles that they are need to be oriented with ill effects of neuroticism. Proper assessment and orientation should be given to male counterparts in order to alleviate them from ill effects of neuroticism which is a personality trait that is characterized by sorrow, irritability, and emotional instability.

Key Words: Personality Traits, Prospective Teachers

Introduction:

Personality may be defined as the dynamic arrangement of qualities and behavioural patterns that are unique to the individual. Personality impacts a teacher's conduct in a variety of ways, including how they interact with students, the methods they use, and the learning experiences they choose (Murray, 1972). In performing educational activities, it is critical to make effective use of a teacher's personality. While "personality" traits can influence views of good teaching and may influence individual preferences for teaching and learning, the basic attributes associated with effective teaching are gained, improved, and modified throughout the course of a teacher's career. In terms of teaching quality, society is seeking a better education. To fulfill all of these obligations, a teacher must have management or leadership abilities. As a result, each member of the school community must have personality abilities in areas where he or she is knowledgeable and talented. Effective education has a significant impact on students' lives, as personality is closely tied to an organization's performance. Teachers are the nation's builders, and decides the country's future. As a result, teachers have a greater burden of responsibility and stewardship in the development of the country. Only through shaping the character and imparting values in the young ones entrusted to teachers is this feasible.

Need and Significance:

Personality impacts a teacher's conduct in a variety of ways, including interactions with students, teaching methods, and learning experiences. In performing educational activities, it is critical to make good use of a teacher's personality. Even if there is no formal connection between student and instructor, students might learn through a teacher's personality. A desired teaching personality is one in which the teacher's personality contributes to the creation and maintenance of a learning environment in which students feel at ease and are motivated to study. Because of the importance of teacher personality, a lot of study has been done to look into the personality traits of pre-service and in-service teachers, but no specialized research has been done in this area. There has never been a research to assess the personality of prospective teachers at a college of education. This research was carried out in order to address a research gap in this field.

Operational Definitions:

- **Personality Traits:** The personality traits are the set of behaviours as whole and in terms of extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism and openness possessed by the prospective teachers during their internship or pre-service training programme.
- **Prospective Teachers :** Those teachers who undergone two year pre-service training programme offered by the Teacher education training colleges at the undergraduate B.Ed level.

Objectives:

- To determine the level of personality traits of prospective teachers.

- To determine whether there is a significant gender difference in the personality traits of prospective teachers.

Hypotheses:

- The prospective teachers have an average degree of personality traits.
- The personality traits of prospective teachers do not differ significantly on their gender.

Methodology:

In this study, the researcher used a normative survey as a method. The sample is three hundred and three prospective teachers from ten different B.Ed colleges in Salem and Namakkal Districts of Tamilnadu who are doing their first year of college of education. The sample was chosen using a basic random sampling procedure by the investigator. Personality traits of prospective teachers' data was collected using standardized inventory by John, O. P., and Srivastava, S. (1999). The mean, standard deviation, and t-test were used to analyse the data for taking suitable decision and interpretation.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Hypothesis 1: The prospective teachers have an average degree of personality traits.

Table 1: The Level of Personality Traits of Prospective Teachers

Personality Traits	Low		Average		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Extraversion	93	30.7	133	43.9	77	25.4
Agreeableness	80	26.4	141	46.5	82	27.1
Conscientiousness	90	29.7	117	38.6	96	31.7
Neuroticism	78	25.7	136	44.9	78	25.7
Openness	76	25.1	138	45.5	89	29.4
Whole Personality	80	26.4	145	47.9	78	25.7

According to the Table.1 above, 30.7, 43.9, and 25.4 percent of prospective teachers have a low, medium and high degree of Extraversion. 26.4, 46.5, 27.1 percent of prospective teachers have a low, average and high level Agreeableness. 29.7%, 38.6%, and 31.7 % of prospective teachers have a low, medium, and higher degree of Conscientiousness. 25.7, 44.9, and 25.7 percent of prospective instructors have a low, medium, and high level of Neuroticism. 25., 45.5, and 29.4 percent of prospective teachers have low, average, and high level of Openness. For whole sample, majority of prospective teachers (49.7) have average personality features. As a result, the stated hypothesis that the prospective instructors' personality traits are average is accepted.

Hypothesis 2: The personality traits of prospective teachers do not differ significantly on their gender.

Table 2: The Test of Significance of Difference in Means Scores for Personality Traits between the Male and Female Prospective Teachers

Personality Traits	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Critical Ratio	Significant
Extraversion	32.56	3.420	31.56	3.878	2.373	S
Agreeableness	36.13	4.312	35.13	4.694	1.933	NS
Conscientiousness	35.98	4.451	35.20	4.360	1.533	NS
Neuroticism	31.49	3.390	30.70	3.767	2.024	S
Openness	38.38	5.386	37.04	4.523	2.313	S
Whole Personality	174.53	18.297	169.62	18.363	2.320	S

The personality attributes of male and female prospective instructors are interpreted as follows in the table above: Male prospective teachers had a mean score of 32.56 with a standard deviation of 3.420 on the Extraversion personality characteristic. The average score for female prospective instructors is 31.56, with a standard deviation of 3.878. The difference in averages in scores of male and female prospective teachers yielded a t value of 2.373. Even at the 0.05 level, this result is more than table, indicating that the critical ratio is considerable. This demonstrates that there is a considerable difference in the Extraversion attribute of personality between male and female prospective teachers.

The Agreeableness personality characteristic has a mean score of 36.13 and a standard deviation of 4.312 for Male prospective teachers. The average score for female prospective teachers is 35.13, with a standard deviation of 4.694. The difference in mean scores between male and female prospective teachers yielded a t value of 1.933. Even at the 0.05 level, this figure is smaller than the table, indicating that the critical ratio is not significant. This shows that there is no significant difference in the Agreeableness personality characteristic between male and female prospective teachers.

Male prospective teachers had a mean score of 35.98 with a standard deviation of 4.451 on the Conscientiousness personality characteristic. The average score for female prospective teachers is 35.20, with a standard deviation of 4.360. The difference in mean scores between male and female prospective teachers yielded a t value of 1.533. Even at the 0.05 level, this figure is smaller than the table, indicating that the critical ratio is not significant. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the mean Conscientiousness attribute of personality between male and female prospective teachers.

Male prospective teachers had a mean score of 31.49 with a standard deviation of 3.390 on the Neuroticism personality characteristic. The average score for female prospective teachers is 30.70, with a standard deviation of 3.767. The difference in mean scores between male and female prospective teachers yielded a t value of 2.024. Even at the 0.05 level, this figure is higher than the table, indicating that the critical ratio is significant. This indicates that there is significant difference in the mean Neuroticism attribute of personality between male and female prospective teachers.

The Openness personality characteristic has a mean score of 38.38 and a standard deviation of 5.386 among male prospective teachers. The average score for female prospective teachers is 37.04, with a standard deviation of 4.523. The difference in mean scores between male and female prospective teachers yielded a t value of 2.313. Even at the 0.05 level, this figure is higher than the table, indicating that the critical ratio is significant. This indicates that there is a substantial difference in the mean Openness attribute of personality between male and female prospective teachers.

Male prospective instructors had a mean score of 174.53 with a standard variation of 18.297 for overall personality. The average score for female prospective teachers is 169.62, with a standard deviation of 18.363. The difference in mean scores between male and female prospective teachers yielded a t value of 2.320. Even at the 0.05 level, this result is more than table, indicating that the critical ratio is considerable. This demonstrates that there is a considerable variation in general personality between male and female prospective teachers.

As a result of the stated null hypotheses, it may be concluded that male and female prospective teachers differ considerably in terms of extraversion, openness, neuroticism, and overall personality. However, there are no substantial differences between male and female prospective teachers in terms of agreeableness, and conscientiousness. As a result, it may be stated that there are considerable differences in personality qualities between male and female prospective teachers.

Discussion:

This study revealed that the female prospective teachers have low personality traits in total as well as other personality attributes like extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness except neuroticism when compared to their male counterparts. This should be revamped through their proper orientation and training at the time of their internship programme. Female prospective teachers have lower neuroticism is a positive sign when compare to their counterparts. So they are more resistant to stress and have less unpleasant feelings such as fear, sorrow, worry, and guilt. The low level of neuroticism further indicates that they are more satisfied, confident, and steady during their internship pre-service training programme. They have less physical and psychological difficulties, as well as less stress, than their male prospective teachers. Male prospective teachers have higher neuroticism than female prospective teachers. Distress and unhappiness are linked to higher neuroticism (Van den berg, P. T., & Feij, J. A., 2003) Individuals with a higher level of neurosis are more likely to be unhappy with themselves and their life. They are more prone to complain about minor health issues and to feel uneasy in a variety of circumstances (Watson, 1967). According to studies, having high scores on the other personality qualities leads to better results, such as better relationships, more positive feelings, and even greater earnings. Higher levels of neuroticism are linked to an increased risk of mental and physical health problems, as well as addiction.

Recommendations:

It is strongly recommended that measurement of personality traits should be adopted in organisational set-up to assist and in the selection of human personnel in all recruitment process. It might be suitable to begin a conversation on the use of personality traits assessments in teacher education faculty to aid candidate selection.

Personality has already been proposed as a selection strategy for entering teacher preparation (Thornton, Peltier, & Hill, 2005) and teaching practice (Kennedy, 2012). In many countries, teacher trainee selection methods are not founded on strong theory-based or evidence-based models. As a result, our findings provide early empirical support for the significance of personality trait evaluations, particularly conscientiousness and agreeableness, in academic systems that place a premium on student-teacher interactions and student-teacher self-efficacy. Some schools may have assigned students to teachers based on pre-existing information about the student educational outcomes (Kalogrides, Loeb, & Beteille, 2012). This practice of student outcomes based teacher appointment should be avoided and it should be given more importance at the time pre-service training programmes at B.Ed level. Teachers are important drivers of student success in the immediate term, such as academic success (Hattie 2009), as well as in the future, such as college attendance, labor market earnings, and in personal life too (Chetty et al. 2014). So, the teacher educator should build a classroom environment that allows and improves the personalities of future teachers. Parents may also play a

part in moulding the personalities of future teachers. When the personalities of prospective teachers improve, so does their achievement and it help to shape the personality traits of the future students life too. The government may also include personality development classes as compulsory part of the curriculum at B.Ed college level, so that prospective teachers' personalities are gradually enhanced during the academic year.

Conclusion:

All of the Personality qualities (extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, neuroticism, and openness to experience) of prospective instructors are average, according to the findings of this study. This research might be useful as a starting point for tackling the difficult challenge of selecting the greatest teachers. The fact that a teacher must possess knowledge and qualification, as well as particular personality attributes, makes finding competent teachers for schools even more challenging (Andersen, Jon., 2006). All of the aforementioned qualities are required of a good instructor. Furthermore, a good teacher is a good leader who contributes to a decent society.

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